

Best Practice Report

Work Package 4 Archives

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The Work Package on Archives (WP4) best practice report comprises four parts:

1. Introduction

2. A summarised account of the research conducted by a selection of researchers that addresses some of the research themes

3. Methods

4. Impacts

1.

Introduction to WP4 Archives Best Practice Report

Work Package 4 (WP4): This work package explores the central role the archive plays in assessing the ways in which historical and concurrent spatial practices effect short and longer-term democratic exchange and opinion formation in urban spaces and how, in turn, they contribute to urgent contemporary themes. The themes addressed by the Spacex-rise ERs and ESRs in this WP are largely focused around the negative societal impacts that neoliberal value systems have given rise to. They include: the rise of fascism; the housing and homelessness crises across Europe; the growth of precarious forms of labour including platform capitalism which have led to overwhelming feelings of busyness, despair and ultimately burnout; the struggle to survive that artist-led institutions face in light of the contraction of welfare state systems and gentrification practices; the emphasis on competition and individualism in Higher Level arts education; and an increase in gender-based violence.

Keeping in mind that the archive has historically been instrumentalised by power as a means of reproducing the status-quo, a focus on the archive's decolonisation is also central to this work package. Specifically the role the archive can play in empowering marginalised and oppressed groups to tell their own stories, while also functioning as a reparative memory site capable of ameliorating social divisions and transforming conflicts.

'What does a constituent archive look like?' is a question posed by the Van Abbemuseum as part of the museum's transition to a 'constituent museum'. The 'constituent archive' is a model that puts relationships at the centre of its operations and considers the user/visitor as part of a constituent body involved in collaboration and coproduction. Building on these debates and issues, WP4 researchers have been exploring how the archive can be variously reimagined and reconfigured as a 'constituent archive' and as 'an archive of the commons', and how it can adapt to take on board the types of knowledge and knowledge communities that these approaches necessitate.

The WP4 researchers have also been testing how transdisciplinary, cross-sector and practice-based research methodologies – including deep mapping and emotional mapping – can be applied to both the creation of new 'itinerant' archives and to research of existing more traditional archives. They have also extended the definition of what an archive can be to include a network of outdoor pedagogical sites, and the infrastructures of art, architecture and urban space.

The following overarching research question that shapes WP4 is 'What role does the archive play in understanding how historical and concurrent spatial practices address issues of democratic exchange and conflict? What are the limitations of extant archiving models and how can the archive be reimagined and reconfigured as a common, centralised shared resource? It's stated objective is to analyse historical and concurrent knowledge stored in archives on the role spatial practices play in addressing issues of democratic exchange and conflict resolution. Finally,

its aim is to reimagine the archive as a universal and centralised resource that is accessible to multiple users from community groups, commissioners, planners and policy writers. The emphasis of WP4 will be on the history and legacy of spatial practices, how they are recorded, documented and re-accessed through the archive. The following research themes (RT9-12) were identified at the start of this research action and the WP4 researchers has been addressing them, as will be mapped in section 2.

RT9: Art as a Means for Investigating the Archive: ERs and ESRs will produce new (spatial) practice projects in order to reinvigorate and democratise the use of the archive.

RT10: Counter-mapping as Open Source Archives for Transforming Conflicts will activate the archive, taking it on the road to test how it can be reimagined and reconfigured as open source for use in conflict transformation.

RT11: Activating and Accessing the Archive will reimagine the archive for multiple users;

RT12: Grass Roots Practices: Documentation and the Archive will analyse existing spatial projects in the archive to find ways of articulating art policy and methods through archival materials.

2.

Research

What follows is a summarised account of the research undertaken by a selection of ER and ERS in the Archives and Culture Value Work Package, mapped against how they have addressed the research themes: RT10-RT12.

(i) [RT10: Counter-mapping as Open Source Archives for Transforming Conflicts will activate the archive, taking it on the road to test how it can be reimagined and reconfigured as open source for use in conflict transformation.](#)

Taking RT10 as their starting point, five of the researchers set about exploring how the archive can be reimagined and reconfigured for use in conflict transformation. Paul Jackson's research at Prague City Gallery explored the ways antifascist cultures develop emotional connections to ideals such as democracy and personal liberty and how these conceptualisations of affect can mobilise antifascist conflict transformation. He is currently developing a project with Prague City Gallery around Czech artist's responses to antifascism. Rosemary Grennan's research, also in Prague at The Academy of Fine Arts, investigated the role that digitised activist archives of the anti-globalisation protests that took place in the city during the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and World Bank summit, can play in building archival networks and solidarities across borders. She is developing a website of digital archival footage drawing from various collections in London in order to map to these to historical events and locations in Prague. Tom O'Dea's research at Kunstverein am Rosa-Luxemburg Platz (KRLP) continued his investigation of the role knowledge embedded in the lived experience of a city can play in conflict transformation. Focusing on the location of his host organisation on Rosa Luxemburg Straße, he explored the significance of linguistic embeddings of place through place names, and how, under neoliberal globalisation, a street with an embedded history of communism and trade-unionism is today host to platform capitalism. Working with a local activist community centre, Offline and staff at the KRLP, O'Dea's research culminated in an event titled 'It's easier to talk about [platform capitalism] when having dinner together', which explored the movement of people and resources in response to European Colonisation, the contemporary conditions of European immigration law, and the use of digital labour platforms. During her secondment to the National Technical University of Athens (NTU), Fani Arampatzou's research explored the role that historical feminist archival research – which includes accounts of the living conditions of experimental feminist communities of the late nineteenth and early twentieth century – can play in contemporary housing reform and mitigating against gender-based violence. The outcome of her research is an article that examines the role architecture plays in implementing the feminist call of family abolition. In a related vein, Avril Coroon secondment to Angewandte University of Applied Arts in Vienna led to her investigation into how the social housing system of 'Red Vienna' can inform social housing policy in the context of Ireland where there is currently a housing crisis.

(ii) [RT11: Activating and Accessing the Archive will reimagine the archive for multiple users;](#)

Responding to RT11, three of the researchers focused on how the archive can be reimagined and activated for multiple users. During her secondment to the Van Abbemuseum in Eindhoven, Michelle Browne elected to respond to the prompt of

what a constituent archive might look like. She conducted a forensic examination into the relational legacy of on a participatory work in the museum archive by the Danish artist collective Superflex. Superflex's original work comprised a workshop within the museum where replicas of Untitled (Wall Structure) by the conceptual artist Sol Lewitt (1972) were reproduced 23 times and then distributed to visitors who had won a public lottery. Browne tracked down and contacted the winners, fourteen years on, and held interviews with the four respondents at the locations where they had installed their Sol Lewitt works. These interviews comprise an edited audio essay that explores the relational legacy of this project, alongside a discussion of the critical and practical concerns of the work in relation to the evolution of the constituent museum. It will be inserted into the museum archive. Lukasz Risso's secondment to the University of Modena (UoM) focused on conducting research into the liberatory potential of (an)archival materials and their capacity to foster contemporary political struggles. Working with researchers from UoM, he contributed to the creation of an ephemeral and itinerant archive of the history and memory of the Villaggio Artigiano (Artisan Village) – a semi-autonomous, self-sufficient suburb of Modena. Christa-Mia Lerm Hayes' research across a number of secondments (Project Arts Centre, Dublin and Sirius Art Centre, Cobh), is focused on the examination of the legacy of the artist Brian O'Doherty, and how he can be understood as someone who drew attention to the infrastructures of art as both archives and affordances for social action.

(iii) RT12: Grass Roots Practices: Documentation and the Archive will analyse existing spatial projects in the archive to find ways of articulating art policy and methods through archival materials.

Responding to RT12, six of the researchers focused on the role the archive can play in articulating and supporting the creation of art policy. Through her research at the National Technological University Athens (NTU), Emer Grant investigated the role of the archive in promoting and nurturing collective models for the development of artist-led institutions that are robust enough to survive the threat to their sustainability caused by neoliberal economic model. Her research focused on the context of Athens where tourism, the refugee crisis, the rise in Air b-n-b economies, and Golden Visa schemes have converged to create a climate where artist-led practices and institutions are struggling to survive. Through archival research, participatory workshops, interviews and observational studies, her research seeks to engage diverse publics including core organisations across public, private, and charitable sectors, and facilitate international discursive exchange around sustainable models and policies for reform. During her secondment to the University of Amsterdam (UvA), Jiřka Hlaváčková employed deep mapping and emotional mapping to record the legacy of artist-led interventions in post-industrial sites and how they can contribute to the empathic transformation and diversification of these areas to promote mutually inclusive ways of living together in urban space. Her research, which spans a number of sites in different European cities, will culminate in a compendium of strategies for artistic and urbanist approaches to intervening in and transforming urban post-industrial areas into more diversified places that promote mutually inclusive ways of living together in urban space. During his secondments at the University of Amsterdam (UvA) and Helsinki, Ryan Hughes, founder and director of the Coventry Biennale (CB), has been investigating the ways in which international artists can create opportunities for access, shared understanding and increased relevance with local audiences and communities in Coventry. Inspired by how cycling is a pivotal feature of Dutch and Finnish life, he has also been reflecting on and testing how active travel – especially walking and cycling – can support opportunities for access, mutual support and the relevance of contemporary art programmes for local audiences, communities and cultural tourists in Coventry. Emma Mahony has mined the archive of the commons at Casco Art Institute:

Working for the Commons in Utrecht to support research into alternative readings of cultural value that forefront the production of social wealth through practices of care and commoning. Taking Casco as a case study, she has written an article that examines how the practice of commoning might be applied to publicly funded cultural institutions in order to make their operations more equitable. Together with Seoidin O'Sullivan, who also conducted research into Casco's archive, she is also testing out commoning and unlearning exercises in the context of the art school with a view to the students unlearning neoliberal values such as 'individualism', 'competitive behaviour', 'that failure is only negative' and the overwhelming feeling of 'busyness' that contemporary precarious labour gives rise to. O'Sullivan is producing a guide to teaching the commons in the art school. During his secondment to Stroom Den Haag, Gareth Kennedy explored how cultural institutions and universities that have outdoor pedagogical/ecological spaces can adapt to work with seasonal time in order to become more resilient, ecologically responsive, and happier spaces for their human and more-than-human constituents. He is currently framing this nascent network as a 'living' archive of outdoor biodiverse pedagogical sites.

3.

Methodologies

For most researchers in the archive work package their secondments began with an initial period of immersion in the cultural landscape of their host organisation before expanding out to the city and country. This included meetings with staff members from the host institutions, introductions to a network of local artists, curators, architects, designers, urbanists and community members. Out of this, the SpaceX-rise ERs and ESRs investigated archival holdings, participated in research groups, contributed to seminars, conducted interviews, staged workshops and engaged in observations studies.

Many of the researchers in this work package were involved in testing how transdisciplinary, cross-sector and practice-based research methodologies can work alongside more traditional forms of archival research. Paul Jackson employed a 'history of emotions' approach, and Jitka Hlaváčková explored the role of 'deep mapping' and 'emotional mapping'. Gareth Kennedy's focus encompassed practices centered around the urban commons, critical ecologies and rhizomatic pedagogy, and Lukasz Risso experimented with collaborative education, collective research, and interdisciplinary exchange. Emer Grant organised participatory workshops, interviews and observational studies. Ryan Hughes conducted studio and site visits with artists, observed sub-cultural practices and explored the cycling networks of Amsterdam and Helsinki and how they supported access to cultural institutions.

Some researchers challenged and extended the definition of what an archive can be. For Gareth Kennedy it extended to a network of outdoor ecological/pedagogical sites, for Tom O'Dea it was condensed into forms of linguistic knowledge embedded in a place through their street names and Christa-Mia Lerm Hayes put forward a case for infrastructures of art itself to be understood as an archive to which new meanings could be layered.

4.

Impacts

The following is a summary of the range of impacts by type, that the secondments had both in the host and home cities.

Academic Articles

The following researchers wrote academic research articles: Fani Arampatzidou wrote the article 'Family Abolition and the "Home" (2024) currently unpublished. Christa-Mia Lerm Hayes, wrote a number of related articles and book chapters including ones for Visual Artists' New Sheet (July-August 2023); The Brooklyn Rail, May 2023; and Charting Space: The Cartographies of Conceptual Art, 2023; "Supervising Art Researchers and Performativity: Reverse Mentoring, Ethics, Adjacency and Consilience", Sternberg Press (forthcoming). Emma Mahony, wrote a number of academic articles including: 'Commoning the Art Institution, Casco Art Institute: Working for the Commons, A Case Study' (2025) currently unpublished; 'Why have there been no great artist-mothers? (after Linda Nochlin)', The Journal of Aesthetics & Protest, February 2024; and 'Beyond the neo-liberal value discourse towards a concept of social wealth', Art & the Public Sphere, 9:1&2, July 2021, pp. 145-162

Conferences

Jitka Hlaváčková initiated and co-organized an international conference on new landscape aesthetics and artistic research in September 2024 that was attended by a number of Spacex researchers.

Workshops

As part of the Fuori Dal Tracciato festival, Lukasz Risso co-organised a collaborative workshop aimed at creating an ephemeral and itinerant archive of the history and memory of the Villaggio Artigiano. During the event, by valorising the importance of grassroots printing and publishing, we produced various publications, zines and pamphlets that presented a community perspective on Villaggio Artigiano and the work done by the host institution in recent years. Christa Mia Lerm Hayes delivered the summer school Brian O'Doherty: Reading Time at Sirius Arts Centre, in June 2023. Emerging from their research into unlearning and commoning at Casco, Emma Mahony and Seoidín O'Sullivan have staged a number of student-led undergraduate and postgraduate workshops at NCAD in 2024 and 2025.

Talks / Teaching

Emma Mahony invited a number of spacex researchers seconded to Dublin, to contribute to teaching on the MA Art & Social Action at NCAD. They included Lua Volland from Stroom Den Haag who gave a lecture and seminar on human rights and precarious labour in 2023, and Benedetta Bronzini from Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia who delivered a seminar on participatory theatre in 2024. Paul Jackson delivered a talk on 'fascism and the history of emotions theories' to students at Academy of Fine Arts in Prague in 2024. Avril Coroon delivered a talk

on her artistic research and practice to the masters students at the school of Social Design at the Angewandte in 2024. Christa Mia Lerm-Hayes gave a talk at Project Arts Centre (PAC): “Soon (In 45 Years’ Time)” Gallery talk and discussion with Colin Darke, in 2022. Lerm-Hayes also delivered a talk at Van Abbemuseum Eindhoven, entitled “Re-Installing Institutions: Kabakov, memory and vigilance”, in 2024.

Artworks/Events

Michelle Browne has created an audio essay that explores the relational legacy of the Superflex’s 2010 Free Sol Lewitt project alongside a discussion of the critical and practical concerns of the work in relation to the evolution of the constituent museum. It will be added to the Van Abbemuseum’s constituent archive. Tom O’Dea, working with the Berlin-based activist community centre, Offline and staff at the KRLP, staged an event titled ‘It’s easier to talk about [platform capitalism] when having dinner together’ in Berlin in 2023. The event explored the conditions that shape ‘organisation’, including the history of European Colonisation, the movement of people and resources in response to this, the contemporary conditions of European immigration law and the use of digital labour platforms. The menu was a series of potato-based dishes that connected to each of these prompts.

Curated Exhibitions

Christa-Mia Lerm Hayes from the University of Amsterdam (UvA) curated the exhibition: Brian O’Doherty: Reading Time, at Sirius Arts Centre, Cobh, in May 2023. Ryan Hughes from Coventry Biennale (CB), secured investment from Mondriaan Fonds in the Netherlands to present a solo exhibition at the Coventry Biennale by an early career artist from Guadeloupe, Clemence Lollia Hilaire, that he was introduced to during his secondment at the UvA. Hughes also established a new health and wellbeing programme called The Coventry Biennale Cycle Club that is contributing to the CB audience development programme. The club, which meets weekly to explore artist spaces, workshops, food, and drink in West Midlands emerged from research he carried out at UvA around cycling infrastructure and their relationship to the built environment and specifically arts centres. Jitka Hlaváčková was introduced to the curator Megan Hotger during her secondment to the UvA and they are collaborating on an exhibition and publication ‘Art of Activism’, which will take place at Prague City Gallery in autumn 2025.

Platforms / Policy

Emer Grant is creating an exchange platform between Athens and Northampton, culminating in presentations at both locations on inclusive spatial practices, public exchange, and diversity promotion. She intends to integrate her research findings into the opening program of the new Arts Collective building in Northampton, scheduled for February 2025.

Establishment of New Research

Gareth Kennedy’s secondment to Stroom Den Haag has led to inclusion of FIELD in the nascent Art Research Gardens Network led by Anna Colin of Goldsmiths, London. Together with partners in 6 other locations – including Van Eyck Academy, Gerrit Rietveldt, Goldsmiths and partners in Tangiers and Limoges – they have applied for a Curiosity Award, which would facilitate movement between all partners to ‘go see’ and participate as guests and hosts in return. Jitka Hlaváčková is preparing an application for an international multiannual grant from

the European Cooperation Projects 2025 (Creative Europe Programme) with the involvement of other members of the Spacex community.